

INNOVATIVE HYBRID SOLAR COLLECTOR FOR SUSTAINABLE HEAT AND POWER SUPPLY**Mysak S.***Candidate of Technical Sciences, Researcher at the Department of Automation and Computer Integrated Technologies**Lviv Polytechnic National University, St.. S. Bandery 12, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013***Shapoval S.***Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor of the Department of Heat and Gas Supply and Ventilation**Lviv Polytechnic National University, St.. S. Bandery 12, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013***ІННОВАЦІЙНИЙ ГІБРИДНИЙ СОНЯЧНИЙ КОЛЕКТОР ДЛЯ СТАЛОГО ТЕПЛОПОСТАЧАННЯ ТА ЕНЕРГОЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ****Мисак С.Й.***Кандидат технічних наук, науковий співробітник кафедри автоматизації та комп'ютерно інтегрованих технологій**Національний університет «Львівська політехніка», вул. С. Бандери 12, м. Львів, Україна, 79013***Шаповал С.П.***Доктор технічних наук, професор кафедри Теплогазопостачання і вентиляції**Національний університет «Львівська політехніка», вул. С. Бандери 12, м. Львів, Україна, 79013***Abstract**

The article examines the efficiency of using a hybrid thermal photovoltaic solar collector (HTPSC) in heat supply systems. The main objective of the study is to analyze the parameters that affect the thermal and electrical efficiency of the collector to maximize its performance.

Анотація

У статті розглядається ефективність використання гібридного теплового фотоелектричного геліоколектора (ГТФГК) у системах теплопостачання. Основна мета дослідження – аналіз параметрів, що впливають на теплову та електричну ефективність колектора для максимізації його продуктивності.

Keywords: solar radiation, thermal efficiency, electrical efficiency, hybrid thermal photovoltaic solar collector; energy supply.

Ключові слова: сонячне випромінювання, тепла ефективність, електрична ефективність, гібридний тепловий фотоелектричний геліоколектор; енергопостачання.

According to alarming forecasts of the United Nations, the deterioration of the ecological situation on the planet has necessitated the development of a comprehensive action plan [1] for implementing sustainable development principles. In this context, the ratification of the Paris Agreement [2] became one of the key steps. Projections show that if current greenhouse gas emission levels persist over the next 20 years, Earth's temperature may increase by 1.5°C. This requires urgent measures to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions [3]. To achieve the set goals, an analysis of the European Union's energy sector policy was conducted [4], resulting in the implementation of the European Green Deal, oriented toward a sustainable development strategy [1]. Within this initiative, a number of regulatory documents aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions have been developed and enacted, such as [5,6,7]. An important role is also played by the promotion of renewable energy sources, which is established, for example, in EU Directive 2018/2001 "On promoting the use of energy from renewable sources." Additionally, the European Commission approved an energy conservation plan [8]. To accomplish these tasks, it is necessary to reduce the

use of traditional energy sources that operate on fossil fuels. This encourages more active involvement of renewable and non-traditional sources, such as vibration energy [9] or solar energy. This requires developing new technologies [10] and improving existing solar energy supply systems [11], applying modern technologies. One of the key directions is the development [12,13] and improvement [14,15] of devices that allow efficient use of solar energy for simultaneous production of thermal and electrical energy through the application of hybrid solar collectors. The problem of optimizing solar energy use is creating modern constructive and technological solutions that will ensure maximum effective absorption of solar radiation and its conversion into thermal and electrical energy with minimal losses. This includes combining photovoltaic panels and thermal collectors into a single integrated system, optimizing heat exchange processes, and increasing insulation levels through improving structural elements and applying innovative materials. After all, hybrid systems have their drawbacks. In particular, almost 90% of solar radiation is absorbed by the surface of photovoltaic panels, and only 15% of the absorbed energy is

converted into electrical energy, while almost 10% is converted into thermal energy [16,17,18]. In this context, it is proposed to combine thermal and electrical components in hybrid systems, adding concentrators that can significantly increase heat exchange efficiency [19]. The implementation of such solutions will contribute to reducing dependence on fossil fuels, cutting greenhouse gas emissions, and supporting sustainable development. To reduce the impact of these drawbacks and increase the efficiency of the photovoltaic-thermal collector, the authors proposed conducting computer modeling of a system equipped with such a solar collector.

The aim is to analyze the functioning of a hybrid solar collector in heat supply systems, as well as to identify parameters that significantly affect its thermal and electrical efficiency. This is necessary to achieve maximum thermal and electrical efficiency of the equipment under given operating conditions.

The article analyzes the functioning of a hybrid energy supply system (HES), which includes a hybrid thermal photovoltaic solar collector (HTPSC). The schematic diagram of this system is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Hybrid energy supply system

Legend:

1 – solar radiation source; 2 – thermal photovoltaic part of HTPSC; 3 – photovoltaic cells; 4 – thermal insulator; 5 – protective transparent cover; 6 – thermal part of HTPSC; 7 – solar radiation concentrators; 8 – thermal sensors; 9, 12 – pipelines for heated and cooled heat transfer fluid; 10 – thermal accumulator (TA); 11 – circulation pump; 13 – control unit; 14, 15 – pipelines for cooled and heated heat transfer fluid in the consumer system

According to Fig. 1, the hybrid energy supply system with a hybrid thermal photovoltaic collector (HES with HTPSC) consists of two main blocks: a hybrid thermal photovoltaic collector, which includes a photovoltaic part 2 and a thermal part 6, and a thermal accumulator (TA) 10. These blocks are connected by pipelines for heated 9 and cooled water 12, which serves as the heat transfer fluid in this system. The circulation of the heat transfer fluid occurs thanks to pump 11, which ensures the transfer of absorbed thermal energy from the solar radiation source 1 to the TA, from where water is then supplied to end consumers. The operation of the circulation is controlled by control unit 13 based on information received from thermal sensors 8. To reduce heat losses and increase the efficiency of the HTPSC, the design includes a thermal insulator 4 and solar radiation concentrators 7. The installation generates electrical

energy using photovoltaic cells 3, which receive solar radiation through the transparent cover 5.

Experimental studies of the solar system were conducted at an ambient air temperature of 15°C. The HTPSC plane was oriented perpendicular to the direction of the sun's rays. Parameter values were recorded every 5 minutes. During each experiment, the mass flow rate of the heat transfer fluid in the installation remained constant.

Experiments on the HES with HTPSC were conducted under constant azimuthal deviation angle of the normal to the HTPSC from the local meridian $\alpha = 50^\circ$ and tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon $\beta = 50^\circ$ (Fig. 2 – Fig. 7), as well as for $\alpha = 50^\circ$ and solar radiation intensity in its plane $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$ (Fig. 8 – Fig. 13).

The thermal efficiency of the HTPSC η_{HTPSC} , depending on the solar radiation intensity in its plane $I_t [\text{W/m}^2]$, is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} on the intensity of solar radiation in its plane I_m by $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, $G = 0,015 \text{ kg/m}^2 \text{ s}$

According to Fig. 2, for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$, with an increase in the intensity of solar radiation in the HTPSC plane I_t , its thermal efficiency η_{HTPSC} decreases nonlinearly: threefold from 2.42 at $I_t = 100 \text{ W/m}^2$ to 0.81 at $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, and by an additional 22%

to 0.63 at $I_t = 900 \text{ W/m}^2$, reducing by a total factor of 3.8.

In Fig. 3, a graphical dependence of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s] is presented.

Fig. 3. Dependency of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} as a function of the mass flow rate of the heat transfer fluid G , at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

From Fig. 3, it follows that at a solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane of $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, its thermal efficiency η_{HTPSC} is almost independent of the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G in the system and ranges from 0.79 to 0.81.

Fig. 4 shows the variation in the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$, depending on the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t [W/m²].

Fig. 4. Dependency of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ as a function of the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t , at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $G = 0.015 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$.

From Fig. 4, it follows that for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$, with an increase in the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t , the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ decreases nonlinearly: threefold from 2.12 at $I_t = 100 \text{ W/m}^2$ to 0.71 at $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$,

and by an additional 22% to 0.55 at $I_t = 900 \text{ W/m}^2$, decreasing by a total factor of 3.8.

The graphical dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s], is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

According to Fig. 5, at a solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane of $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ slightly increases from 0.67 at $G = 0.005 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$ to

0.71 at $G = 0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$ and to 0.73 at $G = 0.025 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$, increasing by a total of 9%.

Fig. 6 presents the dependence of the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} on the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t [W/m^2].

Fig. 6. Dependence of the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} on the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $G = 0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$.

According to Fig. 6, for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$, with an increase in the solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane I_t , the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} increases by 7%, from 0.128 at I_t

$= 100 \text{ W/m}^2$ to 0.137 at $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, and by a total of 8.6% to 0.139 at $I_t = 900 \text{ W/m}^2$.

The graphical dependence of the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s] is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Dependence of the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

According to Fig. 7, at a solar radiation intensity in the HTPSC plane of $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} is almost independent of the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G and remains at 0.137.

The thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} depending on its tilt angle to the horizon β [deg] is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} on its tilt angle to the horizon β , at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, and $G = 0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2\cdot\text{s)}$.

According to Fig. 8, for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2\cdot\text{s)}$, as the tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon increases, its thermal efficiency η_{HTPSC} decreases by 15%, from 0.95

at $\beta = 10^\circ$ to 0.81 at $\beta = 50^\circ$ and $\beta = 90^\circ$, remaining almost unchanged for β between 50° and 90° .

Fig. 9 presents the graphical dependence of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s].

Fig. 9. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of HTPSC η_{HTPSC} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

From Fig. 9, it follows that at a tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon $\beta = 50^\circ$, its thermal efficiency η_{HTPSC} is almost independent of the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , as its values range between 0.79 and 0.81.

Fig. 10 presents the dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon β [deg].

Fig. 10. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon β , at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, and $G = 0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2\cdot\text{s)}$.

According to Fig. 10, for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2\cdot\text{s)}$, as the tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon increases, the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ decreases by 15%, from 0.83 at $\beta = 10^\circ$ to 0.71 at

$\beta = 50^\circ$, and remains almost unchanged at 0.7 for $\beta = 90^\circ$.

Fig. 11 presents the graphical dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s].

Fig. 11. Dependence of the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

According to Fig. 11, at a tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon $\beta = 50^\circ$, the thermal efficiency of the HES with HTPSC $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ slightly increases from 0.67 at $G = 0.005 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$ to 0.71 at $G = 0.015$

$\text{kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$ and to 0.73 at $G = 0.025 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$, increasing by a total of 9%.

Fig. 12 presents the dependence of the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} on its tilt angle to the horizon β [deg].

Fig. 12. Dependence of the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} on its tilt angle to the horizon β , at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, and $G = 0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$.

According to Fig. 12, for a specific mass flow rate of the heat carrier G , which is $0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$, the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} decreases by 1% as the tilt angle of the installation to the horizon β increases from 10° to 90° .

The graphical dependence of the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G [kg/s] is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Dependence of the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} on the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G at $\alpha = 50^\circ$, $\beta = 50^\circ$, and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$.

According to Fig. 13, for a tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon $\beta = 50^\circ$, the electrical efficiency of its photovoltaic cells η_{FE} increases by 0.5% as the specific mass flow rate G increases from $0.005 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$ to $0.015 \text{ kg/(m}^2 \cdot \text{s)}$, and then remains almost unchanged.

Thus, for an azimuthal deviation angle of the normal to the HTPSC from the local meridian $\alpha = 50^\circ$ and a tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon $\beta = 50^\circ$, at a solar radiation intensity in its plane $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, the change in the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G from 0.01 kg/s to 0.05 kg/s has little effect on the thermal and electrical characteristics of the HTPSC. However, at $G = 0.03 \text{ kg/s}$, an increase in I_t from 100 W/m^2 to

500 W/m^2 reduces η_{HTPSC} and $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ threefold, from 2.42 to 0.81 and from 2.12 to 0.71, respectively. An increase in I_t from 500 W/m^2 to 900 W/m^2 further decreases η_{HTPSC} and $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ by 22%, to 0.63 and 0.55, respectively. Conversely, the electrical efficiency of HTPSC η_{FE} increases by 8.6% when I_t changes from 100 W/m^2 to 900 W/m^2 .

For $\alpha = 50^\circ$ and $I_t = 500 \text{ W/m}^2$, at $\beta = 50^\circ$, the thermal efficiency η_{HTPSC} and the electrical efficiency η_{FE} of HTPSC are almost independent of the variation in the mass flow rate of the heat carrier G from 0.01 kg/s to 0.05 kg/s , while $\eta_{HES \text{ with HTPSC}}$ increases by 9%, from 0.67 to 0.73.

For $G = 0.03$ kg/s, when β increases from 10° to 50° , the thermal efficiencies η_{HTPSC} and $\eta_{\text{HES with HTPSC}}$ decrease by 15%, from 0.95 to 0.81 and from 0.83 to 0.71, respectively, and remain almost unchanged when β increases further to 90° . The variation in the tilt angle of the HTPSC to the horizon β from 10° to 90° has almost no effect on the electrical efficiency of the HTPSC photovoltaic cells η_{FE} , reducing it by only 1%.

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